

DIGITAL TERRORIST AND SOCIAL MEDIA AUDIT ELEMENTS

Organizing an attack has been simplified with just one click, in the simplest and easiest way of our age. In this way, which we call digital, it completely puts the security of the country, the security of people, and the security of property at risk. By hacking a state's database, it can block that country's city signaling, satellite systems, National Radio- TV broadcasts, and carry out opposing propaganda by making pirated broadcasts. Likewise, by hacking your personal databases, they can access our bank accounts and private correspondence and easily empty our accounts from banks' systems, or they can take our private documents and serve them to other channels as leverage.

They are observed as one of the best effective ways in factors such as National Electricity, Gas Networks and city security systems and Traffic signals, CSMS- ECS, which are on our agenda the most. So what is Digital Terrorism?

What does digital terrorism mean?

Digital terrorism is defined as the use of computers or computer systems against individuals and property for the purpose of intimidating or oppressing a government or society in order to achieve a certain political and social goal.

Spread of Digital Terrorism and Digital Terrorists through give way methods

As we mentioned in the introductory text above, digital terrorists pursue positions against the most sensitive strategically located facilities and applications of states, and they can also prepare the ground for social events by broadcasting on social media that will cause public uneasiness, to give an example of these. Asparagas can make calls to the public with fabricated press reports and completely fabricated pictures and documents. All people are in social media at all times with their GSM phones, which are indispensable in the digital age. As individuals, they can share on broadcast websites, social forms and messaging groups for these platforms and can organize instantly. It can create sympathizers. With these approaches, perception is created by putting pressure on the social network, especially on young people and students. Today, many actions, digital frauds and digital thieves can seize the property of many people due to these perceptions.

The role of digital terrorism in preventing it from becoming widespread

Consider the recent rise of terrorism; there is only one reason why it has spread widely around the world and everywhere has turned into a dangerous zone: The mass of people and terrorists have made good use of the rapid development of digitalization and technology. When states are late in taking timely preventive measures, it is necessary to take control by increasing the necessary measures and controls on media organs such as Social Media Programs and Sharing and messaging sites. Communication should be established with the countries where the social media companies and providers in question are located and joint control networks should be developed. It should establish a monitoring unit and supervision unit under the name of the National Social Media Control Center (NSMCC).

States individually take measures and precautions to combat digital pirates. It is trying to combat this by establishing units and personnel who browse social media. In order to combat terrorism, it is necessary to be much more professional and rational in order to solve the problem by creating and activating units that will specifically deal with Digital Terrorism, in addition to the units combating cyber crimes in the Homeland Security units.

Digital Terror in Turkey

If we try to document the attitude of social media towards digital terrorism in Turkey through comparative discourse analysis, a model for relationality will be proposed through this method. We can take it under control by increasing the controls by establishing the National Social Media Control Center (USMDM) by leading the world and in our country . On the other hand, it will create digital terror agents outside our cyber security units and provide the opportunity to reach the target easily.

For some incomprehensible reason, social media inevitably plays a role in the fight against digital terrorism in the world and in Turkey. Thanks to the audit of the National Social Media Control Center (USMDM), we should realize the awareness of responsibility and liability in social media, review its advantages, priorities and responsibilities and make an accurate definition of the relationship between Social Media, state, society and digital terrorism; It will be the solution to many debates between the media and the rights and responsibilities of the individual and society. Our country's security forces are immediately intervening in the publications of people and individuals who make digital terrorism propaganda and to keep information pollution, hatred crimes, e-commerce and digital banking under control in the general protection of national security networks in the future. However, it will provide the opportunity to immediately intervene in the actions and behaviors of the incident at the keyboard.

We must continue to take steps and develop for our clean future, our country's security, our future, our children, our country's unity and world peace.